

Multi-Scale Remote Sensing of Wildfire Impact and Post-Fire Vegetation Recovery in the Cross-Border Karst Landscape

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Abstract: Wildfires in the Karst Plateau (sln. Kras, ita. Carso) cross-border karst plateau between Slovenia and Italy are becoming more frequent, of larger scale and more devastating. To map burned areas across large areas and track vegetation recovery at finer scales, remote sensing at different scales should be applied. This paper presents a multi-scale remote sensing workflow developed within the KARST FIREWALL 5.0 project for wildfire monitoring in karst landscapes. Satellite imagery was used for regional cross-border analysis of past fires from the 1980s onward, while UAV surveys supported seasonal monitoring at selected local pilot site. Sentinel-2 imagery was used where available for new fires and Landsat data for older fires. Burned areas and vegetation status were assessed with BAIS2 and BAI for satellite images and NDVI for satellite and UAV images. Burn scars were delineated from differences in indices and converted into vector polygons. Out of 682 initial fire records, burned-area polygons were derived for 171 fires. UAV monitoring during the 2025–2026 season was conducted at pilot site in Miren-Kostanjevica municipality which was affected by two past wildfires (2003 and 2022). Seasonal RGB and NDVI interpretation at pilot site showed that vegetation recovery is ongoing but spatially uneven, with better regeneration along vegetation edges and more favourable microsites (dolines), and slower recovery on exposed rocky dry surfaces. Additionally, Sentinel-2 seasonal scenes confirmed the broad recovery trend at landscape scale.

Keywords: wildfire; karst; Sentinel-2; Landsat; UAV; post-fire vegetation recovery.

1 Introduction

Wildfires are one of the major natural hazards in Mediterranean and sub-Mediterranean landscapes (Filipponi 2018). The Karst Plateau (sln. Kras, ita. Carso) on the Slovenian-Italian border is a fire-prone karst landscape where rocky terrain, shrub cover (abandoned pastures), dry grasslands, and mixed forest create mosaic of land-use heterogeneity.

Remote sensing provides repeated observations that are suitable to burned-area mapping and post-fire vegetation assessment. BAI and BAIS2 are widely accepted indices for burned area detection, whereas NDVI remains one of the standard indicators of vegetation status (Chuvieco et al. 2002, Filipponi 2018, Tucker 1979). Sentinel-2 and cloud-based processing environments further improved these

analyses by combining suitable spectral bands with efficient access to large image archives (Drusch et al. 2012, Gorelick et al. 2017).

The study covered municipalities of Miren-Kostanjevica and Komen in Slovenia and Duino-Aurisina in Italy, the area that was devastated during 2003 and 2022 wildfire events. Within the KARST FIREWALL 5.0 project a remote sensing database was prepared to support cross-border environmental monitoring, post-fire vegetation assessment, and later restoration planning. The aim of this paper is to present the workflow used for fire mapping and vegetation assessment and to summarize the main outputs obtained from satellite and UAV data.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Satellite workflow

Satellite data were collected for the wider cross-border fire-prone area. The fire inventory was assembled from two existing datasets, one for the Slovenia and one for Italy. Both were filtered to retain only events within the target municipalities. Because used medium-resolution satellite imagery limits reliable identification of very small events, only fires larger than 0.5 ha were retained for detailed processing. Satellite images were accessed and processed in Google Earth Engine and final vector products were prepared in ArcGIS Pro. Priority was given to Sentinel-2 imagery when available, while Landsat scenes were used for older periods. Images with more than 30% cloud cover were excluded. The remaining scenes were manually screened for noise and localized clouds over the study area and removed where necessary. To reduce random effects and masking errors, the first suitable pre-fire and post-fire scenes were used or, when needed, several scenes were combined by median calculation. Burned areas were identified from BAI and BAIS2, while vegetation status was assessed with NDVI (Chuvieco et al. 2002, Filipponi 2018, Tucker 1979). Difference images were thresholded and vectorized. Thresholds were selected separately for each event because image quality, season, and surface background varied between cases. For selected recent fires, NDVI-based vegetation assessment was carried out after the initial delineation.

2.2 UAV survey

Seasonal UAV monitoring focused on local vegetation and surface conditions in the pilot area. Surveys in Miren-Kostanjevica were carried out on 27 May 2025, 16 July 2025,

Figure 2. Pilot area photographed by UAV with an RGB camera in four seasons (spring - upper left, summer - upper right, autumn lower left, winter - lower right).

Figure 3. Pilot area NDVI in four seasons (spring - upper left, summer - upper right, autumn lower left, winter - lower right).

UAV images (Figure 2 and Figure 3) and show the same general pattern of recovery at landscape scale, but with strong interpretative limits due to clouds and weather conditions in general. The autumn scene provides the clearest view of the burned landscape and shows widespread but uneven revegetation across the fire affected area. The summer scene is partly useful, whereas the spring and winter scenes are strongly affected by cloud cover, cloud shadow and reduced seasonal comparability, which makes fine-scale interpretation less reliable or in some cases even impossible.

The Sentinel-2 series is therefore well suited for regional mapping of the burned perimeter and for tracking broad vegetation trends across the whole cross-border area, but it cannot resolve the high-scale heterogeneity visible in UAV products. In particular, Sentinel-2 data (Figure 4) do not clearly separate narrow rocky bands, edge regeneration, or the seasonal contrast between broadleaf and evergreen vegetation that becomes visible in the pilot site. The two data sources converge on the same overall finding of ongoing but incomplete post-fire recovery, while differing in the level of ecological detail they provide.

Figure 4. Wider cross-border area covering all three pilot areas captured by the Sentinel-2 satellite in four seasons.

4 Discussion

The results show that satellite and UAV data can serve different but complementary roles. Satellite imagery provides the basis for a harmonized historical database across the full Slovenian-Italian study area, while UAV data provide the detail needed for repeated local monitoring of pilot site. This combination is especially useful in karst environments, where a single data source rarely captures both long-term regional patterns and fine local variation. The combined reading of RGB and NDVI products indicates that the 2022 fire affected area is not recovering as a uniform vegetation cover, but as a spatially uneven mosaic shaped by rocky substrate, exposure, vegetation edges and land-cover structure.

The pilot-site analyses refine this general picture. Repeated RGB and NDVI interpretation helps separate broadleaf and shrub regrowth from more stable evergreen patches. This distinction matters for interpretation of NDVI, since lower autumn and winter values do not automatically imply degradation, but often reflect leaf-off conditions in deciduous vegetation. Local UAV products with higher temporal resolution in the whole vegetation season are therefore essential for distinguishing delayed recovery from normal phenological variation.

The workflow also revealed several limits of post-fire mapping in karst conditions. Not all filtered wildfire events could be mapped successfully, especially small fires and fires from periods with limited image availability. For older events, the lower revisit frequency of Landsat, winter cloudiness, and phenological mismatch between pre-fire and post-fire scenes often obscured the fire signal. Similar problems also affected the seasonal Sentinel-2 comparison for the 2022 fire perimeter, where autumn provided the clearest regional view, whereas spring and winter scenes were partly masked by clouds and therefore less suitable for site-level interpretation. Despite these limits, the combination of BAI, BAIS2 and NDVI proved operationally useful because it separated initial burned area from later vegetation assessment and linked regional cross-border mapping with repeated site-based observation.

5 Conclusions

This paper presented a remote sensing workflow for fire monitoring in the cross-border karst landscape, based on the database prepared within the KARST FIREWALL 5.0 project. The workflow combines satellite archives for regional historical fire mapping with UAV surveys for local seasonal monitoring of pilot areas.

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